

ADVANTAGES OF USING MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN FINE ART LESSONS

Smaylova Gulmari Yuldashevna

Docent of the National Center for Teaching Pedagogues to
New Methods of the Republic of Karakalpakstan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049450>

Abstract: The article provides information about the advantages of using modern educational technologies in art classes, the essence of the pedagogical process of the art teacher, and the joint activities of the teacher and the student.

Key words: Fine art, modern teaching technologies, education, teacher, method

It is the eternal dream of our people to raise a person to be perfect in all aspects, and our ancestors were constantly looking for ways to teach enlightenment, spirituality and culture to the young generation - to lead them to perfection, as well as laws and regulations. This led to the emergence of visual art science among pedagogical sciences. Because, the achievement of enlightened and spiritual perfection of a person is carried out under the leadership of the science of visual arts, among the pedagogic sciences.

Educational purpose, content, form, method and means are traditional categories used to analyze the content of educational processes. It is these categories that appear as the subject of the activity of a pedagogue who organizes the educational process in a certain subject, specialty or specialty. The mentioned pedagogical categories act as a systematizing factor of the legitimacy and criteria of the pedagogical activity directed in accordance with the purpose.

Pedagogical categories noted for many years have been sufficient for the realization of goals at the level of social demand of the society. In certain periods, a group of pedagogues evaluated the level of pedagogic activities performed in all periods. They are, in particular, the vagueness of the definitions and descriptions given to pedagogical concepts, the lack of some categories describing educational processes, the lack of coherence between educational goals, content, form, style and teaching tools. who have been constantly criticizing the situation. They emphasize that the concept of "methodology" has a high level of subjectivity. In reality, the educational results are determined by the student's successful passing of pedagogical processes.

The essence of the pedagogical process of a fine arts teacher is reflected in the content of the joint activity of the teacher and the student, in this process the pedagogue helps the student to overcome the difficulties that have arisen. The main essence of pedagogical assistance is expressed by the description of the pedagogical process, its orientation to a certain goal, as well as the tasks to be solved in the field of personality formation and education.

A visual arts teacher can convey information, demonstrate, remind, give insight or advice, guide, justify, counsel, remedy, empathize, inspire, express interest and respect, and support demand. -helps in ways such as support.

Modern teaching technologies are a complex integral (whole, organic system, in which the skills and competencies determined on the basis of educational goals are the way to acquire theoretical knowledge by students, to educate them in certain spiritual and moral qualities. is reflected as a certain regulated view of the elements of directed pedagogical activity. Here, the visual arts teacher determines educational goals, selects and develops content, organizes educational processes, It is necessary to take into account the determination of methods and tools, as well as the level of qualifications of teachers, the method of evaluating the achieved results. The collective application of the mentioned criteria determines the nature and technology of the educational process.

A fine arts teacher sets a pedagogical task in the process of designing educational technology, and it is necessary to pay special attention to its solution. The content of the teacher's activity aimed at designing teaching technology that ensures the solution of pedagogical tasks is formed on the basis of methods, forms and tools.

The main factors determining the content of the pedagogic activity of a fine art teacher are: the type of management, the type of information exchange processes, the types of information transmission tools and the management of cognitive activities.

Based on the concept of an activity-based approach to the teaching process, its organization can be based on the following logical sequence: initially, the description of the content of the educational material, the purpose of learning it (levels of mastery), as well as the conditions of the pedagogical task is analyzed. Then, appropriate methods of teaching and a system of managing students' cognitive activities will be developed. Based on this, a list of teaching tools will be compiled.

The teacher of visual arts combines the integrated system of methods and educational tools created by this method with organizational forms, that is, develops a specific technology. Generalized modern educational technologies are aimed at methodically solving the problem of designing the professional training process aimed at achieving a pre-planned result.

Today, there is a need to develop pedagogical technologies related to personal activity approach, critical-creative thinking, problem solving, decision-making and team cooperation. At the same time, modern educational technologies are effectively used in the practice of educational institutions.

General pedagogical and didactic tools for all stages of education, improving the effectiveness of independent work on the basis of the student's (or student's) programming knowledge, imagination and skills, increasing their interest in scientific thinking, academic subjects, deepening their professional knowledge, theoretical and is to increase their activity during practical training. Jakhan's pedagogical experience confirms that the possibilities of modern pedagogical technologies to interest students (or pupils) in science and to increase their activity in independent work are endless.

Today's task of education is to teach students to use the flow of information wisely, to be able to operate independently in the conditions of the information education environment that is increasing day by day. For this, it is necessary to provide them with the opportunity and conditions for continuous independent work. Accordingly, we would not be wrong to say that it is an urgent problem of today to prepare general professional subjects through information and communication technologies and to try to form more knowledge and skills of young people based on the demands and wishes of young people.

Therefore, the modern educational technology of the pre-planned educational process includes a system of methods, educational methods, goals, tools, opportunities for teachers and students to work together, and a complex of achieving final results. embodies. All this is important in the upbringing of a mature generation, in the formation of the spiritual worldview of young people.

References:

1. J. Yoldoshev "Introduction of modern pedagogical technologies into practice"-T., 2008
2. Muslimov N.A., Usmonboeva M.H., Sayfurov D.M., Toraev A.B. Innovative educational technologies - T.: "Sano standard" publishing house, 2015

